

STUDIES ON THE CHEMISTRY OF RHENIUM. PART III.
COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF QUADRIVALENT
RHENIUM WITH CATECHOL

BY DEBABRATA SEN AND PRIYADARANJAN RÂY

A complex acid formed by quadrivalent rhenium with catechol, having the composition, $\text{H}[(\text{OH})_2\text{Re}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, and its thallium salt have been described. The dissociation constant, k , of the acid has also been determined, which gives a value of 3.2×10^{-6} at 25° .

In continuation of the work described in Parts I and II of this series (*this Journal*, 1953, 30, 171, 181), a complex acid of quadrivalent rhenium with catechol and its thallium salt are now described in the present paper.

The precipitated rhenium dioxide ordinarily does not dissolve in a solution of catechol even when boiled. But on heating potassium rhenichloride with catechol in water, a dark brown solution was obtained from which brown crystals of a complex compound were isolated. It was found on analysis to have the composition $\text{ReO}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The three molecules of water could not be removed without decomposition. The structure of the complex can therefore be represented as: $\text{H}[\text{Re}\cdot(\text{OH})_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ or, $\text{H}_2[\text{Re}\cdot(\text{OH})_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2]$. Potentiometric titration with alkali showed the acid to have a monobasic character. The substance should therefore be represented by the first formula.

The value of k , the dissociation constant, has been found to be 3.2×10^{-5} at 25° . The dissociation constant of catechol is 3.3×10^{-10} at 25° (Euler and Bölin, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, 66, 75). Thus, the complex formation has considerably increased the strength of the acid. The thallium salt of this acid has also been prepared.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aquo-trihydroxo-rheni-catechol.—Pure recrystallised potassium rhenichloride (1 mol.) was treated with catechol (4 mols., Merck's Reagent) in a little water. The mixture was then heated just to boiling in a R. B. flask under reflux and then warmed on the water-bath for about an hour. A dark brown solution was obtained which was cooled, filtered and evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid. The residue was extracted with absolute alcohol to remove potassium chloride. The alcoholic solution was again evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator. The product was then digested with dry and pure ether to remove the excess of catechol. The residue of the complex acid was washed thoroughly with ether and kept in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid.

The substance forms brownish black crystals, which reacts acid in aqueous solution. It is highly soluble in water and alcohol and also in dioxane, but insoluble in dry ether. It is quite stable in acid medium, but slowly oxidises in presence of alkali.

Rhenium was estimated as in the case of rhenigallic acid described before. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by combustion in a semimicro combustion system.

{Found : Re, 51.06 ; C, 19.79 ; H, 2.69. $H[Re.(OH)_3.C_6H_4O_2.H_2O]$ requires Re, 51.10 ; C, 19.78 ; H, 2.75 per cent}.

Potentiometric Titration of the Acid.—The acid was titrated against alkali potentiometrically (cf. Figs. 1-2) (cf. Part II, *loc. cit.*).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

TABLE I

Alkali = 0.1247 M. $t = 25^\circ$. Acid = 0.005 M.

Alkali.	Molar conc	p_H .	p_k .	π .
0.0 c.c.	—	3.00	3.602	0.800
0.5	0.6253×10^3	3.15	3.591	0.734
1.0	1.247	3.42	3.737	0.675
1.5	1.871	3.95	4.152	0.603
2.0	2.494	4.52	4.512	0.495
2.5	3.118	5.20	4.978	0.375
3.0	3.742	6.00	5.526	0.252
3.4	4.240	6.62	5.873	0.152
3.8	4.740	7.54	6.279	0.052
4.2	—	8.93	—	—
5.0	—	9.82	—	—

From Fig. 2, $p_k = 4.5$; $k = 3.2 \times 10^{-6}$.

Thallium salt of the aquo-trihydroxo-rheni-catechol was prepared by the addition of thalious sulphate to a solution of rheni-catechol in water. The insoluble thalious salt separated out as a brown precipitate. This was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and then with a little alcohol. It was finally dried in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid.

The substance forms dark brown crystals, almost insoluble in water and organic solvents, but soluble in dilute mineral acids.

The substance was analysed following the method employed for the thallium salt of rhenigallic acid described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). {Found: Re, 32.84; Tl, 35.87. Tl $[Re.(OH)_3.C_6H_4O_2.H_2O]$ requires Re, 32.80 ; Tl, 35.98 per cent}.